

FACTORS OF PATRIOTIC FEELING FORMATION IN YOUNG PEOPLE

Saparov Bobir Xudayberdievich

Researcher at the National University of Uzbekistan

Abstract. The formation of patriotism is one of the priorities in the field of Secondary Education. Traditionally associated with the increase in the civil-patriotic, spiritual moral, legal and psychological mining of most social institutions that carry out socialization. Introducing patriotism to the level of self-awareness, social activity, Uzbek cultural historical values and Customs is one of the main most important tasks in increasing the patriotic sense of youth. The article is based on a problematic approach to the formation of youth patriotism. Their patriotic directions, values are analyzed. The state, problems and factors of the formation of youth patriotism are considered.

Key words: citizen, civil ministry, Civil, activity, awareness, public activity, Patriot

As a person grows older, their understanding of the Motherland also expands. Every person born and raised in our country, when they say "My Homeland," refers not merely to their home, village, or city, but to the Republic of Uzbekistan. This reflects the patriotic spirit in the hearts of our people. The feeling of homeland means respect and loyalty to our dear and beautiful country. The sense of homeland includes the desire to study the golden heritage and rich history of our people, who have lived in Turan, Transoxiana, Turkestan—lands now known as Uzbekistan. The brave and courageous sons of our nation such as Tomyris, Shirak, Spitamen, Najmiddin Kubro, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, and Temur Malik, who sacrificed their lives for the freedom of the Motherland, serve as eternal examples for us and for the younger generation. For instance, let us recall the unfading courage of our ancestor Najmiddin Kubro. At the heart of his feat lies boundless love and devotion to the Motherland. He once said: "My homeland, my Turan—being separated from you is my fate." "[1]

Patriotism is a deep respect for one's family, the honor of ancestors, loyalty to one's conscience, duty, and word. If a person is not brought up from childhood in the spirit of love and respect for their people, traditions, language, and culture, then a sense of patriotism will not form. The feeling of homeland becomes especially evident when a person is far from their native land. History tells us that the lives of many compatriots who lived abroad for various reasons were tragic and sorrowful.

Patriotism means love and devotion to the Motherland, service to the nation, and the willingness to dedicate one's entire potential—and even life—for this cause. It is one

of the universal human feelings and spiritual values inherent to all peoples, nations, and ethnic groups, refined over centuries. From a historical perspective, patriotism is closely tied to the fate of the homeland in the process of socio-economic development, and to the integrity and independence of the territory where people live. To be proud of the Motherland's past and present, to care for its future, and to protect its interests—this is patriotism. For a deeper understanding of this concept, it is essential to study the works of literary and intellectual figures such as Furqat, Fitrat, Abdulla Qodiriy, Cholpon, Abdulla Avloniy, Usmon Nosir, Hamid Olimjon, Gafur Gulom, Erkin Vohidov, and Abdulla Oripov. To be a patriot means to love the homeland, to do honorable deeds for the people, and to glorify and cherish the nation" [2]. The homeland is the past, present, and future of every person.

Understanding one's duty to the nation and homeland should be the highest ideal. A person should feel they are a part of their homeland and be proud of it. It should be natural not to forget that they were raised on its soil, and not to forget that the homeland expects love and kindness from them. Only then can true happiness be attained. Every society passes its wealth onto the next generation. However, it is a known fact that the new generation does not always know how to manage these resources. There are clear distinctions between the concept of homeland during the Jadid era of the early 20th century, during the Soviet period, and after the country's independence. In the national awakening period, patriotism in the works of Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Fitrat, Haji Muin, and Cholpon was expressed through advocacy, resistance, militancy, and the spirit of struggle. In contrast, literature of the independence period reflects patriotism with gratitude, responsibility, pride, and hope for the future [3].

In Fitrat's poem "Yurt qayg'usi" (The Grief of the Homeland), his views on national liberation are expressed with deep emotional intensity: "Oh great Turan, land of lions! What's the matter with you? How are you? What kind of days are you in? O glorious cradles of the Chinggisids, Timurids, Oghuz, and horsemen!". The feeling of patriotism is reflected in deep knowledge of and pride in one's history, in the careful preservation and transmission of the material and spiritual heritage created by great ancestors, in the continuation of traditions and customs that have become values, and in sincere devotion to the future of the state, the stability of independence, and the greatness of the future. Indeed, at all times, the fate of a nation is determined by the upbringing of its youth. Jadid thinkers also emphasized the importance of proper upbringing for both individuals and society.

Patriotism connects human consciousness with the influence of the environment—one's birthplace, upbringing, childhood and youth experiences, and emotional development. Among the fundamental feelings of every person are respect for the place

of birth, love and care for it, respect for local customs, and lifelong loyalty to this land. Our youth are an invincible force. Our great ancestor Sahibkiran Amir Temur once said, “You can break one stick, but you can’t bend many.” This highlights the importance of knowing one’s national history and culture and, in turn, learning to respect the traditions of other peoples as well[4].

In modern times, instilling a sense of patriotism in youth has become especially relevant. While a great deal of methodological literature is now being published on this topic, it often only addresses separate aspects of patriotic education within specific fields of activity. Patriotism includes love for one’s homeland, pride in one’s people, a sense of belonging, and a desire to preserve and enrich the nation’s heritage.

In various social events and patriotic organizations that unite compatriots to carry out patriotic missions and contribute to the homeland’s development, the first mentors to awaken children's patriotic feelings are parents. The role of the family, school, and mass media in shaping youth patriotism is significant. Social institutions, especially the education system, also play an invaluable role in fostering civic-patriotic and spiritual-moral culture. Today, the primary sources of information for many young people are the internet, television, and video content. Only a small portion of them receive information about patriotism through books, newspapers, or magazines. This creates certain contradictions, as not all information online is accurate, leading to confusion and distraction. Patriotism can manifest on individual, group, and societal levels[4].

Therefore, the family plays a key role in laying the foundation for patriotism and ethical values during childhood. For patriotism to become a core principle in upbringing and to deeply influence a child’s mind and heart, continuous and serious effort is needed. Proposals for developing patriotic qualities in the family environment are essential for schoolchildren. “Patriotism should be instilled in a person from birth—just like kindness, compassion, and diligence.” Parents are their children’s first educators.

Conclusion Today, youth education is one of the most important strategic goals of state policy. Comprehensive personality development is entrusted to general education institutions, and this is seen as a crucial factor in cultivating students’ abilities and inspiring their creativity. Explaining current reforms, historical events in a modern light, and national ideas helps develop students’ ideological awareness and spiritual worldview. Only in this way can a powerful national education system be built—one that inspires bravery, initiative, and national pride in young hearts. While patriotism is often associated with military service, in reality, this feeling encompasses much more. It should not be viewed narrowly. A true patriot is a physically and morally healthy, well-educated, culturally refined person who values family, respects their ancestors,

lives by national traditions, and constantly strives to improve their lifestyle and contribute to the development of their homeland.

REFERENCES

1. Sayfullayev B., Rustamov V. Skill in Organizing Cultural Events. Tashkent. 2015.
2. Khoji Ahmadjon Bobomurod. Islamic etiquette and morality. Tashkent, 2008.
3. Abdurazakova M. et al. Explanatory Dictionary of Peace and Tolerance Terms Editor-in-Chief Q.A. Jo'raev 2005.
4. Mamatov, J. (2022). Parameters of the Connection between Art and Culture. Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT.